

UDC332.1

**DIGITAL TWIN FOR SUSTAINABLE ENERGY DEVELOPMENT:
OPPORTUNITIES FOR KAZAKHSTAN AND MALAYSIA**

ABDUL IZZ MOHAMAD KAMIL, MOHAMAD SYAZLI FATHI

Department of Smart Engineering & Advanced Technology, Faculty of Artificial Intelligence
Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

ZEESHAN AZIZ

School of Science, Engineering and Environment, University of Salford, Salford M5 4NT,
Manchester, United Kingdom.

Digital Twin (DT) technology is gaining recognition as a transformative solution for the energy sector, enabling real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, and lifecycle optimization of infrastructure assets. For emerging economies such as Kazakhstan and Malaysia, where energy systems face pressures from rising demand, renewable integration, and sustainability goals, DT offers strategic benefits. This study examines DT in the context of Kazakhstan and Malaysia, two countries with shared challenges but different energy strategies. A systematic literature review (2018–2025) was conducted to evaluate DT applications across planning, design, construction, and operation stages. Results show that DT enhances forecasting, design optimization, and infrastructure management. It improves system efficiency, reduces downtime, and supports integration of cleaner energy sources. The analysis highlights DT as a flexible tool that adapts to national priorities and conditions. Findings confirm its role as a strategic enabler for sustainable energy development.

Keywords: digital twin, energy infrastructure, predictive maintenance, forecasting, design optimisation

Introduction

The global energy transition requires innovative tools to ensure reliability, efficiency, and sustainability [1]. Kazakhstan, with its vast fossil fuel reserves and has significant renewable energy [2], and Malaysia has a good mix of energy resources like oil, natural gas, coal and renewable energies with its rapidly diversifying energy mix [3], share common challenges: aging infrastructure, growing demand, energy storage and the need to integrate renewable sources [4]. Energy systems in built environments face inefficiencies from reactive maintenance, causing unexpected failures, higher costs, and energy waste. Traditional methods lack predictive capabilities, making advanced solutions essential for optimized performance [5].

Digital Twin (DT) technology, a dynamic digital replica of physical systems, integrates IoT sensors, data analytics, and machine learning for real-time asset health monitoring [6]. In energy infrastructure, DT can extend asset lifespans, reduce downtime, and enhance grid resilience [7]. This paper investigates how DT can support the smart and modernization of energy systems in Kazakhstan and Malaysia.

Research Methodology

The study employed a systematic literature review (SLR) of publications from 2018 to 2025 covering DT applications in energy systems, infrastructure health, and smart grids. Sources included ScienceDirect and Google Scholar. Then it is discussed in the context of Kazakhstan and Malaysia. The countries were selected as a case study as both hold strategic importance in the global energy transition. Kazakhstan is working toward carbon neutrality by 2060 by gradually reducing its reliance on fossil fuels [8], while Malaysia is focusing on significantly expanding its renewable energy capacity to advance its path toward net-zero emissions [9], with the sample of the country the result and discussion can be comparatively based on each country context needs.

Results

Digital Twin (DT) technologies offer solutions to both countries by enhancing forecasting, design, construction, and maintenance of energy infrastructure. However, the expected benefits vary according to each country’s energy context including climate conditions, and development priorities. To highlight these distinctions, Table 1 presents a comparative overview of DT features and their specific benefits for energy infrastructure health in Kazakhstan and Malaysia.

Table 1 - Findings on Digital Twin Features for Energy Infrastructure in Kazakhstan and Malaysia (Comparative benefits)

Infrastructure Stage	DT Features	Key Authors	Kazakhstan (Benefits)	Malaysia (Benefits)
Planning	Predictive analytics	[5], [10], [11]	Forecasts demand & renewable output; supports carbon neutrality by 2060.	Forecasts solar demand in cities; aligns with 31% renewable goal by 2025.
	Cost planning	[12]	Optimizes retrofitting of coal/gas plants with carbon-reduction tech.	Improves budgeting for large-scale solar projects.
	Decision-making	[13], [14]	Data-driven fossil renewable transition pathways.	Guides renewable expansion and smart grid integration.
Design	Risk identification	[15]	Addresses risks from continental climate	Detects solar farm vulnerabilities to storms/humidity.
	Simulation & optimization	[16], [17]	Tests grid upgrades	Enhances smart grid and rooftop solar output by simulation
Construction	Real-time simulation	[18]	Supports efficient delivery of infrastructure construction	Improves solar farm & urban grid construction.
	Risk mitigation	[15]	Enhances worker safety in grid expansion.	Enhance safety during urban renewable projects.
	Cost efficiency & site monitoring	[19], [20], [21], [22]	Improves monitoring in remote sites.	Reduces financing risks; scales solar across Malaysia.
Operation & Maintenance	Predictive maintenance	[5], [10], [11]	Extends life of aging coal/hydro plants; lowers outages.	Improves solar/grid reliability in cities.
	Sustainability	[4], [8], [9]	Increases efficiency in fossil-heavy system, aiding 2060 neutrality.	Accelerates net-zero by improving renewable efficiency.
	Asset management & feedback	[7]	Extends lifespan of infrastructure; builds resilience to climate extremes.	Extends smart grid assets; adapts to tropical climate & demand peaks.

Discussion and Findings

The comparative analysis highlights how Digital Twin (DT) applications generate different but complementary benefits for Kazakhstan and Malaysia across the stages of energy infrastructure. While both countries share the goal of achieving long-term sustainability, Kazakhstan focuses on

managing its reliance on fossil fuels during its transition to carbon neutrality by 2060, whereas Malaysia emphasizes renewable energy expansion to advance its path toward net-zero emissions.

Planning Stage

In Kazakhstan, DT supports predictive analytics and cost planning to forecast energy demand and optimize the gradual transition from fossil fuels. This ensures that infrastructure upgrades and retrofits contribute to emission reduction. For Malaysia, DT enhances renewable energy planning by improving demand forecasting in urban centers and supporting financial planning for large-scale solar deployment.

Design Stage

Kazakhstan benefits from DT in identifying risks related to extreme continental climate conditions and in simulating long-distance transmission upgrades for renewable integration. Malaysia, in contrast, applies DT to address tropical climate vulnerabilities and optimize the design of smart grids and rooftop solar, reflecting its emphasis on urban energy resilience.

Construction Stage

For Kazakhstan, DT improves the management of projects by enabling real-time monitoring and safety measures. This is critical for efficient project delivery across vast territories. Malaysia applies DT at the construction stage to ensure efficiency and cost control in renewable infrastructure expansion, particularly in high-density areas where delays can have significant impacts.

Operation and Maintenance Stage

Both countries achieve long-term benefits from DT in this stage, but with different priorities. Kazakhstan focuses on predictive maintenance for aging fossil-based plants, ensuring reliability during the transition while improving carbon efficiency. Malaysia applies DT to maximize the performance and resilience of renewable and grid assets, directly supporting its net-zero commitments.

Figure 1 – Energy infrastructure Digital Twin Platform

Figure 1 illustrates the structure of a Digital Twin (DT) platform for energy infrastructure across four stages: planning, construction, operations, and optimization. The data layer integrates operational, environmental, structural, and behavioral data. This feeds into the model layer, combining physical assets such as plants, grids, and storage with virtual models for prediction and performance. The service layer supports description, diagnosis, forecasting, decision-making, and control. The application layer enables simulation, real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and demand-supply optimization. Together, these layers provide a pathway for efficiency, reliability, sustainability, and resilience. The framework shows that DT is context-adaptive, aligning with

national priorities and energy strategies. For Kazakhstan, DT enables a managed transition from fossil fuels to renewables. For Malaysia, DT accelerates renewable energy expansion while strengthening system resilience. This confirms DT as a strategic instrument for sustainable energy transitions.

Recommendations

To maximize the benefits of Digital Twin (DT) technologies, both Kazakhstan and Malaysia should integrate DT into their national energy roadmaps to enhance efficiency, resilience, and sustainability. Priority should be given to pilot projects that demonstrate DT's value in grid management, renewable integration, and system modernization. Finally, cooperation can strengthen knowledge exchange, with Kazakhstan contributing insights on fossil-to-renewable transitions and Malaysia sharing lessons on renewable integration, creating a foundation for broader regional energy innovation.

Conclusions

This study shows that Digital Twin (DT) technology provides important advantages for modernizing energy systems, enhancing efficiency, reliability, and sustainability. Its impact varies depending on national priorities and energy contexts, highlighting the need for flexible and adaptive implementation. DT should be viewed not as a single solution but as a strategic tool that can support diverse pathways toward cleaner and more resilient energy futures. By aligning DT adoption with country-specific goals, both nations can advance their energy transition and contribute to global sustainability efforts.

Acknowledgments

The work described in this paper was supported by British Council under Going Global Partnership grant through Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (R.K130000.7356.4B808)

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